

Objectives, Requirements and Implementation of a Service Restoration Algorithm for AC-DC Distribution Grids

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Abstract—With the increasing penetration of DC based devices and the improving performance of power electronics converters, more and more advantages foster the deployment of hybrid AC-DC distribution grids. Although the operating control of AC-DC grids is consistently studied in the literature, several protection aspects need further analysis. This paper focuses on the reliability of AC-DC distribution grids, proposing a Service Restoration (SR) algorithm to efficiently re-energize the disconnected nodes in case of electrical faults. To determine the SR solution, the algorithm inspects multiple criteria together: the number of reconnected nodes, the minimization of power losses, the presence of telecontrolled switches, the criticality of the nodes facilities and the restoration feasibility according to power forecasts. The evaluation of reconfiguration topologies is based on the operational limits of AC-DC converters and energy sources; additionally, the power transfer is controlled by setting as optimization objective the losses minimization. The conducted tests, considering different load and generation configurations, prove the applicability of the proposed algorithm in evaluating the feasibility of reconfiguration topologies and computing the near-optimal SR solution.

Index Terms—Service Restoration, AC-DC, Distribution Grids, Optimal Power Flow, MCDA

I. INTRODUCTION

Due to recent progress in power electronic conversion-related devices, several scenarios result in the advantageous implementation of DC technology instead of traditional AC [1]. In particular, considering the greater utilization of DC based Distributed Generator (DG) and load demands, research activities consider the deployment of DC sub-networks alongside AC power in future distribution grids, connecting the DC generation to the DC consumption and reducing the number of conversion stages [2]. The reliability of electrical distribution grids is a fundamental aspect to be analyzed and guaranteed so that the network can withstand and recover from faults occurrences, ensuring the continuous power supply to end customers [3]. This paper focuses on SR functionality, which

follows the fault clearance and pursues the energization of disconnected nodes by reconfiguring the electrical network [4].

For AC-DC distribution grids the power transfer among AC and DC network sections is optimized by controlling the power converters, as proposed in [5], [6]; anyway, these studies do not consider the reconnection of de-energized loads following a fault. The authors in [7], [8] present genetic SR algorithms to compute the power setpoints for Voltage Source Converters (VSC) that interconnect AC networks; anyway the objective functions combine power losses and switching operations with inconsistent weighting factors. In [9], the restoration approach implements a mixed-integer second-order cone programming to optimize the power supply in AC-DC distribution grids; however the converter losses and the computation of different restoration topologies, as with Normally Closed (NC) switches, are not included. Despite literature works, in deploying SR the candidate solution shall be applicable not only in the operating time instant but also in the successive time period, which accounts for the average duration of permanent faults until the network reparation, by integrating the power forecasts of loads and generators [10].

In this paper we present a general SR method, designed for real-time application, based on graph theory and mathematical programming approaches. The main contributions of this manuscript are:

- An algorithm for AC-DC grids to concurrently re-energize the disconnected nodes, considering their priorities and opening of NC switches, based on an Optimal Power Flow (OPF) to determine the operating setpoints.
- The integration of a Multiple Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) to determine the SR solution by evaluating, in addition to the network power losses, the remote controllability of switches and the applicability in the successive time period with power forecasts profiles.

II. PROPOSED SR ALGORITHM

In the event that an electrical fault occurs in the distribution grid, the protection system acts to promptly isolate the fault area, by opening the nearest upstream and

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$$P_{tot}^{loss} = \sum_{i,j \in N_{AC}} \left(G_{ij} \left(|V_i|^2 + |V_j|^2 - 2|V_i||V_j| \cos(\varphi_{V_i} - \varphi_{V_j}) \right) \right) + \sum_{p,q \in N_{DC}} \left(\frac{V_p - V_q}{R_{p,q}} \right)^2 + \sum_{m \in N_C} P_{C,m}^{loss} \quad (1)$$

downstream switches. The execution of SR outcome is an interim network condition preceding the crew intervention and system reparation, whose total duration is (on average for typical permanent faults) between 2 and 4 hours [11]. SR mitigates the consequences of electrical faults and improves the network reliability indices, which quantify the quality of power delivery.

A. Network Reconfiguration

The SR process starts by computing the candidate solutions for topology reconfiguration, on which the OPF is applied.

The network is modelled according to graph theory and the branches properties include the switches information (presence, status, tripping condition). The disconnected nodes, downstream the fault area, are identified by verifying the electrical connectivity of each node with at least one power source (primary substation or AC-DC converter). Since the algorithm controls the switches within the de-energized area, multiple nodes not interconnected by switches constitute a node group: re-connecting a node group results in energizing all the corresponding nodes.

Due to grid security constraints (voltage and ampacity limits) the SR process could, eventually, re-energize only part of disconnected nodes. Hence the disconnected node groups are classified according to their priorities, by considering:

- 1) The highest value of index λ , pre-assigned by grid operator to each node and representing the infrastructure criticality, in each node group.
- 2) In case the highest λ is the same for multiple node groups, the number of DG and value of revenue compensation.
- 3) In case multiple node groups have equal outcomes from 2), the total nominal power (consumption and generation) in each node group.

The array of prioritized node groups K_N^* displays its elements sorted by the computed priorities. For each node group, the most suitable path toward the power sources is determined by using the Dijkstra's algorithm [12]. Considering two nodes a and b in a graph G , the Dijkstra's algorithm calculates, if exists, the path $G'_{a,b}$ that connects them with minimum impedance of the lines, then minimizing the power losses. These paths determine the Normally Open (NO) switches, whose closures re-energize the node groups maintaining the radiality of AC sub-network. Hence the algorithm provides the array S_{NO} having as sub-arrays the different combinations of NO switches, alternatively operated (as candidate solutions) to re-energize the node groups.

Additionally, in order to extend the set of candidate solutions, the opening of NC switches among node groups, if present, is computed and the Dijkstra's algorithm is re-applied. The array S_{NO}^{NC} includes the combinations of switches whose

Fig. 1. Model of AC-DC converter station.

operations re-energize every node group; the sub-arrays in S_{NO}^{NC} , as many as the number of considered NC, are composed:

- as first element, by the NC switches to be closed
- as successive elements, by the alternative combinations of NO switches to connect the de-energized area, sorted by the priorities of the corresponding node group in K_N^*

The candidate solutions for the SR process are constituted by each sub-array included in S_{NO} and S_{NO}^{NC} .

B. Optimal Power Flow

For each candidate solution the statuses corresponding to NO and, eventually, NC switches are updated, constituting the input for the OPF calculation. This procedure has two goals: to verify the solution according to the grid operational limits and to optimize the power transfer of DG and AC-DC converters.

Each AC-DC converter station is modelled as VSC, shown in Fig. 1. In the deployed operating mode, one AC-DC converter acts as DC slack and sets the corresponding n voltage to 1 p.u. The losses of converter station, P_C^{loss} , aggregates losses of the components such as the ac filter, phase reactor and VSC converter; they are approximated as a quadratic function of the phase current $I_{C,m}$ at node $m \in N_C$ (with N_C as set of converter nodes) [6]:

$$P_C^{loss} = -P_C^{AC} - P_C^{DC} = a_c + b_c |I_{C,m}| + c_c |I_{C,m}|^2 \quad (2)$$

The optimization is structured as Nonlinear Programming (NLP) problem, having as objective function the minimization of network power losses P_{tot}^{loss} in (1); variables are the active and reactive power setpoints for DG, the power and current setpoints for AC-DC converters and the node voltages:

$$\min (P_{tot}^{loss}) \quad (3)$$

$$P_{gen,i}^{AC}, Q_{gen,i}^{AC}, P_{gen,p}^{DC}, P_{C,m}^{AC}, Q_{C,m}^{AC}, V_i, V_p, I_{C,m}$$

Y_{ij} is the element (i, j) of AC admittance matrix, having $\theta_{Y_{ij}}$ as phase and G_{ij} as conductance. φ_{V_i} indicates the phase of voltage at node i , whereas $R_{p,q}$ is the resistance of DC line among p and q nodes. N_{AC} and N_{DC} indicate the sets of AC and DC nodes, respectively.

The constraints for AC-DC distribution grids are:

- Power balance constraints at AC nodes N_{AC} ($i \in N_{AC}$):

$$P_{gen,i}^{AC} + P_{C,i}^{AC} - P_{load,i}^{AC} = |V_i| \sum_{j \in N_{AC}} (|V_j| |Y_{ij}| \cos(\varphi_{V_i} - \varphi_{V_j} - \theta_{Y_{ij}})) \quad (4)$$

$$Q_{gen,i}^{AC} + Q_{C,i} - Q_{load,i}^{AC} = |V_i| \sum_{j \in N_{AC}} (|V_j| |Y_{ij}| \sin(\varphi_{V_i} - \varphi_{V_j} - \theta_{Y_{ij}})) \quad (5)$$

- Power balance constraints at DC nodes N_{DC} ($p \in N_{DC}$):

$$P_{gen,p}^{DC} + P_{C,p}^{DC} - P_{load,p}^{DC} = \sum_{q \in N_{DC}} \left(\frac{V_p - V_q}{R_{p,q}} V_p \right) \quad (6)$$

- AC current at AC-DC converter nodes N_C ($m \in N_C$):

$$(I_{C,m})^2 = \frac{(P_{C,m}^{AC})^2 + (Q_{C,m}^{AC})^2}{V_m^2} \quad (7)$$

- Voltage coupling between AC and DC converter sides (m and n nodes, respectively, as in Fig. 1), considering the range of PWM's converter modulation index $m_{C,m}$ as [0,1] [13]:

$$V_m \leq \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\sqrt{2}} V_n \quad (8)$$

Except for the DC slack converter, having $V_n = 1.0$ p.u.

- AC current limit for AC-DC converters:

$$I_{C,m} \leq I_{C,m}^{MAX} \quad (9)$$

- Reactive power limits for AC-DC converters (as maximum values of absorption and injection), considering $m_{B,m}$ as the converter constraint factor, $S_{C,m}^{nom}$ as the nominal apparent power of the converter and $B_{r,m}$ as the susceptance of converter's phase reactor (k node as in Fig. 1) [6]:

$$-m_{B,m} S_{C,m}^{nom} \leq Q_{C,m}^{AC} \quad (10)$$

$$Q_{C,m}^{AC} \leq |B_{r,m}| V_m^{MAX} (V_m^{MAX} - V_k) \quad (11)$$

- Power limits for AC and DC generators (including DG):

$$P_{gen,i}^{AC,MIN} \leq P_{gen,i}^{AC} \leq P_{gen,i}^{AC,MAX} \quad (12)$$

$$Q_{gen,i}^{AC,MIN} \leq Q_{gen,i}^{AC} \leq Q_{gen,i}^{AC,MAX} \quad (13)$$

$$P_{gen,p}^{DC,MIN} \leq P_{gen,p}^{DC} \leq P_{gen,p}^{DC,MAX} \quad (14)$$

- Power limits for AC and DC lines:

$$P_{i,j}^{AC,MIN} \leq P_{i,j}^{AC} \leq P_{i,j}^{AC,MAX} \quad (15)$$

$$Q_{i,j}^{AC,MIN} \leq Q_{i,j}^{AC} \leq Q_{i,j}^{AC,MAX} \quad (16)$$

$$P_{p,q}^{DC,MIN} \leq P_{p,q}^{DC} \leq P_{p,q}^{DC,MAX} \quad (17)$$

- Voltage limits for AC and DC buses:

$$V_i^{MIN} \leq V_i \leq V_i^{MAX} \quad (18)$$

$$V_p^{MIN} \leq V_p \leq V_p^{MAX} \quad (19)$$

OPF calculations are deployed with real-time measurements and, eventually, forecast values, as explained section II.C.

C. Multiple Criteria Decision Analysis

The MCDA technique quantifies the optimality of each feasible candidate solution according to different attributes.

In the proposed SR algorithm, the attributes are:

- 1) The parameter β , indicating the number of switches, both NC and NO, to be operated in the candidate solution that can be telecontrolled from the utility control centre. Unlike telecontrolled switches, the manually controlled devices have to be operated directly at their location, extending the reconfiguration time by the time-consuming crew intervention [11].
- 2) The power losses of the entire AC-DC network, indicated by P , corresponding to the objective function value in (1) for the candidate solution.
- 3) The parameter η_1 : to ensure that the candidate solution, feasible according to the OPF with real-time data, is still applicable in the near future (e.g. for voltage, power and ampacity constraints), the execution of the OPF is repeated for the successive time frames with input data based on power forecasts. The next four time frames, each one of 15 minutes (according to the common availability of forecast values), are considered; among these, η_1 indicates the number of time frames, from 0 to 4, in which the candidate solution is applicable.
- 4) The parameter η_2 : in case the evaluation in the next hour confirmed the applicability of the candidate solution (hence $\eta_1 = 4$), the analysis is extended by considering successive 12 time frames, covering as total verification period the next 4 hours. The parameter η_2 ranges from 0 to 12, counting the number of applicable solutions in the inspected time frames.

The implemented MCDA is composed by two sequential procedures: Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) and Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS).

The AHP consists of pair-wise comparisons among the attributes, defining the symmetric comparison matrix Γ :

$$\Gamma = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & w_{\beta P} & w_{\beta \eta_1} & w_{\beta \eta_2} \\ \frac{1}{w_{\beta P}} & 1 & w_{P \eta_1} & w_{P \eta_2} \\ \frac{1}{w_{\beta \eta_1}} & \frac{1}{w_{P \eta_1}} & 1 & w_{\eta_1 \eta_2} \\ \frac{1}{w_{\beta \eta_2}} & \frac{1}{w_{P \eta_2}} & \frac{1}{w_{\eta_1 \eta_2}} & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (20)$$

Elements of Γ are the comparison values between the attributes indicated by the subscripts (β , P , η_1 or η_2), ranging from 1/9 (attribute of first subscript is extremely irrelevant with respect to the second one) to 9 (attribute of first subscript is extremely important with respect to the second one), pre-assigned by the network operator with the AHP scale [14].

From Γ the priority vector is obtained, which ranks the four criteria and shows relative weights among them. These

relative weights are combined with the outcomes of each feasible candidate solution (the specific values of β , P , η_1 and η_2) according to TOPSIS [15]. This technique allows to compute the closeness of each candidate solution to the ideal solution, which is composed by the minimum power loss P and maximum β , η_1 and η_2 . The closest candidate solution is designated as the near-optimal solution to be implemented.

D. Complete SR Procedure

The control flow of the proposed SR method is shown in Fig. 2. The SR middleware retrieves, from static and real-time databases, the latest configuration of grid topology, network parameters and data measurements as well as power forecasts. As the fault occurs and is isolated, statuses of switches are updated and the SR algorithm starts: candidate solutions for network reconfiguration are computed, defining the arrays S_{NO} and S_{NO}^{NC} . The following actions are then deployed:

- 1) To each candidate solution reconnecting every disconnected node group with only NO switches (i.e. the sub-arrays of S_{NO}) the OPF is applied. The candidate solutions that satisfy the operational constraints result as feasible and constitute the inputs for MCDA, to determine the near-optimal solution to be implemented.
- 2) In case no one candidate solution from action 1) is feasible (according to OPF constraints, e.g. voltage, power and ampacity limits), the opening of NC switches is considered: the sub-arrays of S_{NO}^{NC} are inspected as candidate solutions via OPF. The near-optimal solution, among the feasible ones, is identified with MCDA described in section II.C.
- 3) In case no one candidate solution from action 2) is applicable, the algorithm deploys only the feasible SR of node groups having the highest priorities. The new candidate solutions become the sub-arrays of S_{NO}^{NC} from which the last element is removed (i.e. a NO switch is not operated). The deployment of OPF and MCDA, for the obtained candidate solutions, is repeated.
- 4) The removal of last NO switches in S_{NO}^{NC} , described in action 3), is repeated until a feasible solution is identified.

The near-optimal solution identified with the MCDA technique is implemented: the corresponding closing and opening commands, for NO and NC switches respectively, are issued to operate the corresponding field devices (manually or remotely, according to the devices features), as well as the controller setpoints for the AC-DC converters and DG as obtained from OPF results. The SR process is then concluded.

III. ASSESSMENT CASES

The programming language Python v3.8 is used to implement the algorithm and, specifically, the OPF applies the solver IPOPT v3.14 with the package Pyomo v6.4. The software platform is hosted in a 64 bit Windows machine with an i5 - 2.5 GHz processor and 8 GB RAM.

Fig. 2. Control flow of the service restoration process

Fig. 3. AC-DC Distribution network for the assessment cases.

The grid test case (shown in Fig. 3) is modelled on the "CIGRE MV Distribution Network Benchmark" in the European configuration, modified to include a multi-terminal DC sub-network [16]: two HV/MV transformer stations (indicated as $SS1$ and $SS2$) feed the AC sub-network at 20 kV, interconnected by AC-DC converter stations (with 3 MVA as nominal power and indicated as $C1$, $C2$ and $C3$) with the multi-terminal DC sub-network at 32.6 kV. The coefficients of converter losses a_c , b_c and c_c are obtained from [6] and correspond to $1.103e^{-2}$, $2.571e^{-3}$ and $2.424e^{-3}$, respectively.

Fig. 4. Load and generation profiles

The switches, included in the AC sub-network, are represented by black and white squares (as normally closed and normally open switches, respectively); among them, telecontrolled switches are indicated with the subscript t . The parameters of the modelled network are reported in [16]: the buses host loads aggregated in the categories "residential" and "industrial"; specific nodes includes DG from renewable sources, particularly Photovoltaic (PV) and wind turbine units.

The power values of loads and DG depend on the measurement time (corresponding to OPF deployment) according to the daily profiles shown in Fig. 4. These power profiles values are used as input for the OPF both in the actual time of fault occurrence (from field measurements) and in the future time frames (as loads and generation forecasts, to compute the parameters η_1 and η_2). The profiles relate to average summer working day in Germany: for wind turbine generation, residential and industrial loads are acquired from [17], [18]; whereas the PV profile is obtained considering a low cloudiness level with the software tool presented in [19].

In the test case, due to a fault in node 3 the protection system opens the switches $S1$, $S2$ and $S3$ to isolate the fault area. Consequently, the de-energized nodes (marked with yellow circles in Fig. 3) correspond to buses 7, 8, 9, 10, 11. Considering the presence of NC switches $S6$ and $S7$ as well as the criticality indexes and DG presence, the priorities of the three node groups are: $K_N^* = [[9], [10, 11], [7, 8]]$. To re-energize these switches, the switches combinations for the candidate solutions are computed (according to the procedure described in II-A), defining the arrays:

$$S_{NO} = [[S5], [S8], [S9]]$$

$$S_{NO}^{NC} = [[[S7], [S8, S5], [S8, S9]], [[S6], [S5, S8], [S9, S8]]]$$

To be noted that switches order reflect nodes order in K_N^* .

The values of comparison parameters to build matrix Γ are reported in Table I. Accordingly, the normalized AHP eigenvector is computed: the suitability of the candidate solution in the next four time frames has the highest importance (η_1 , 57.2%); then, in descending order, the suitability in the next

TABLE I
AHP COMPARISON PARAMETERS

	$w_{\beta P}$	$w_{\beta \eta_1}$	$w_{\beta \eta_2}$	$w_{P \eta_1}$	$w_{P \eta_2}$	$w_{\eta_1 \eta_2}$
AHP Value	5	1/4	1/3	1/8	1/7	4

TABLE II
OUTCOMES OF ASSESSMENT CASES ACCORDING TO MCDA RESULTS

	Time Frame	Candidate Solution	β	P [kW]	η_1	η_2	MCDA Closeness
Case 1	21	<u>S5</u>	1	93.2	4	0	34.3%
		<u>S8</u>	0	99.7	4	0	0%
		<u>S9</u>	0	83.7	4	6	65.7%
Case 2	59	<u>S5</u>	1	247.2	4	6	61.1%
		<u>S9</u>	0	218.4	4	12	38.9%
Case 3a	46	<u>S6-S9-S8</u>	1	369.1	0	0	100%
Case 3b		<u>S6-S9</u>	1	249.9	4	12	100%

sixteen time frames (η_2 , 25.2%), the use of telecontrolled switches (β , 13.5%) and the total power losses (P , 4.1%).

Case 1 In the first assessment case the fault occurs at time frame equal to 21. The three candidate solutions, sub-arrays of S_{NO} , are validated as suitable according to the OPF constraints; hence, the evaluation following the MCDA procedure is performed. The results of MCDA indicate the solution $S9$ as the closest to the ideal solution (65.7%).

Case 2 The fault in the second assessment case occurs at time frame equal to 59. In this case, only two candidate solutions ($S5$ and $S9$) suit the operational constraints and are evaluated in the following time frames. According to MCDA outcomes, $S5$ is implemented as solution (closeness to ideal solution equal to 61.1%).

Case 3a The assessment case $3a$ deploys the fault occurrence at time frame equal to 46. The solutions as sub-arrays of S_{NO} are not suitable according to OPF constraints, hence the solutions as sub-arrays of S_{NO}^{NC} are inspected; among them, only $[[S6], [S9, S8]]$ is feasible and is implemented.

Case 3b As for the assessment case $3a$, also in the $3b$ the fault occurs at time frame equal to 46, but partial presence of DG is considered by limiting the nominal power of each unit to 60%. Consequently, the solution computed at case $3a$ is not applicable and only part of the de-energized nodes can be reconnected: among the candidate solutions as sub-arrays of S_{NO}^{NC} , the last ordered switches are discarded. The candidate solution $[[S6], [S9]]$ is the only one applicable, according to OPF outcomes, and it is then implemented.

Table II reports the specific values of MCDA analysis in the different assessment cases. The choice of AHP comparison parameters, according to user's settings, determines the SR solution being implemented, as indicated by the MCDA closeness values. Moreover, the OPF deployed in the successive time periods (with power forecasts) allows to identify the upcoming unfeasibility of candidate solutions and integrating this outcome in the MCDA analysis.

TABLE III
POWER SETPOINTS OF DG AND CONVERTERS FOR THE SELECTED SOLUTIONS

	Case 1 S9	Case 2 S5	Case 3a S6-S9-S8	Case 3b S6-S9
$P_{C,2}^{AC}$ [MW]	-5.694e-1	-2.229e0	-2.926e0	-2.136e0
$Q_{C,2}^{AC}$ [kvar]	3.648e-1	1.082e+1	1.917e+1	9.835e0
$P_{C,6}^{AC}$ [MW]	1.058e0	4.479e0	4.031e0	2.673e0
$Q_{C,6}^{AC}$ [kvar]	2.663e+2	1.422e+3	1.024e+3	6.540e+2
$P_{C,12}^{AC}$ [MW]	-9.910e-1	-4.178e0	-4.247e0	-4.160e0
$Q_{C,12}^{AC}$ [kvar]	2.038e-2	8.409e-2	1.233e-1	1.700e-1
$P_{gen,4}^{AC}$ [MW]	0	1.283e-2	1.826e-2	1.095e-2
$P_{gen,5}^{AC}$ [MW]	0	1.922e-2	2.742e-2	1.643e-2
$P_{gen,6}^{AC}$ [MW]	0	1.920e-2	2.740e-2	1.642e-2
$P_{gen,8}^{AC}$ [MW]	0	1.923e-2	2.739e-2	1.639e-2
$P_{gen,9}^{AC}$ [MW]	0	1.924e-2	2.740e-2	1.642e-2
$P_{gen,10}^{AC}$ [MW]	0	2.566e-2	3.654e-2	off
$P_{gen,16}^{DC}$ [MW]	0	1.923e-2	2.739e-2	1.640e-2
$P_{gen,18}^{DC}$ [MW]	0	1.921e-2	2.738e-2	1.638e-2
$P_{gen,19}^{DC}$ [MW]	1.215e0	1.420	1.287e0	7.720e-1

The power setpoints (active and reactive power for AC-DC converters and active power for AC and DC DG) are presented in Table III. The converters power losses, accounting in the deployed cases between 15.6% and 26.7% of P_{tot}^{loss} , has to be necessarily included in OPF in order to accurately determine the near-optimal solution.

To assess the field deployment, each assessment case is repeated 50 times; the average computation time (since the initiation of SR until the solution values are published in the database) is equal to 14.22 s (with a standard deviation equal to 1.23 s), satisfying the requirement for the real-time implementation. The duration of SR, for smart grids that deploy advanced automation services, is estimated at 4 minutes [20]; the margin with the presented computation time confidently suggests the feasibility of the proposed algorithm even with larger-scale networks.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents an innovative algorithm for SR, specifically tailored for AC-DC distribution networks. The candidate solutions of network reconfiguration re-energize the highest number of disconnected nodes according to their priorities and grid operating constraints. The pair-wise comparison of multiple criteria allows to precisely control the SR objectives, resulting in different outcomes of MCDA, and the extension of OPF analysis with forecast profiles prevents the implementation of SR solutions that become unfeasible within the inspected time period. Moreover, the suitability of OPF to determine the near-optimal power setpoints for DG and AC-DC converters, whose losses are included in the model and have a significant impact in determining the SR solution,

is proved via the different assessment tests. Successive extensions of the proposed algorithm, in future research, will introduce relaxation techniques to overcome the non-linearity of the proposed OPF approach.

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